

Title: Big data

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INTRODUCTION:

The purpose of this conference is to define the term of big data. First the big data are characterized through the model of 3V to 5V extended. The problematic of big data is distinguished from that of Business Intelligence. The economic and societal challenges associated with big data are discussed by presenting various examples of use in different areas of activity. Then, are introduced several great methods and techniques associated with storage and operation / analysis of these big data.

AIM:

After the conference people would be able to define Big data and know the characteristics of Big data.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Our ability to collect “big data” has greatly surpassed our capability to analyze it, underscoring the emergence of the fourth paradigm of science, which is data driven discovery. In this conference, we look at how data-driven techniques are playing a big role in deciphering processing-structure-property-performance relationships in materials, with illustrative examples of both forward models (property prediction) and inverse models (materials discovery).

KEYWORDS:

Big data | storage | big data | analytics

BIOGRAPHY:

Papa has completed his Master Mathematics and computer science from University of Gaston Berger of Saint Louis and Master Studies from African Institute for Mathematical Science of Senegal (AIMS-Senegal), .He is the Data Scientist of NEUROTECH SA Senegal, a B2B company working in the field of innovation and new technology